

GESTATIONAL AGE AND RELIGION AS CORRELATES OF EFFECTS OF HEALTH EDUCATION ON THE LEVEL OF KNOWLEDGE OF ANAEMIA PREVENTION AMONG PREGNANT WOMEN IN RIVERS EAST SENATORIAL DISTRICT OF RIVERS STATE

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Abstract

This study investigated the effects of gestational age and religion on the level of knowledge of anaemia prevention among pregnant women in Rivers East senatorial district of Rivers State. Two research questions were answered and two hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. A multi-stage sampling procedure was adopted to select a sample size of 600 hundred respondents for the study. Data was collected using a structured questionnaire and analysis was carried out using SPSS version 25.0. Analytical tools such as mean, standard deviation and analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) at 0.05 alpha level was employed. The findings of the study showed that effect of the intervention on the preventive behaviour was found to be significant based on religion [$F = 0.027$, $p < 0.05$]. The study concluded that, health education has a significant effect on preventive behaviour towards anaemia among pregnant women in Obio/Akpor. It was recommended among others that, maternal health care professionals including gynecologists and obstetricians should give more attention to the prevention of anaemia among the pregnant women during their antenatal visit by making information relating to it available to them.